

Creation of type specimen Wikidata items via OpenRefine

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[Gingidia haematitica holotype specimen](#). Allan Herbarium, Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research, [CC BY 3.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

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Introduction

This documentation is intended to assist the staff of the Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research group of the New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute (WMLR) as well as other Wikidata editors in the bulk creation of natural history type specimen Wikidata items via OpenRefine (<https://openrefine.org/>). For information on the other methods that can be used to bulk create Wikidata items see the following

<https://information-services.ed.ac.uk/help-consultancy/is-skills/wikimedia/wikidata/data-wikidata>.

Wikidata notability criteria

Before creating a Wikidata item the editor should consider whether the concept to be covered by the item is notable for the purposes of Wikidata. The Wikidata notability criteria is covered in this Wikidata policy document <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Notability>.

Type specimens are arguably notable for the purposes of Wikidata as they are a clearly identifiable material entity that have been described using serious and publicly available references. Type specimens are frequently referred to in scientific literature when the taxonomy of species and subspecies are discussed.

The existence of type specimen items also fulfills a structural need in Wikidata as a Wikidata item for a type specimen is needed to ensure a species or subspecies item can link to its taxonomic type via the [taxonomic type](#) (P427) property.

Properties used to enrich taxon Wikidata items. Siobhan Leachman and Heidi Meudt, [CC0](#), via [Wikimedia Commons](#)

Wikidata type specimen data model

When creating and enriching a type specimen Wikidata item it is best practice to follow the [Wikidata type specimen data model](#) set out in the [Wikidata WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model](#). This model ensures that any type specimen Wikidata created will be consistent and facilitates the reuse and querying of those Wikidata items.

Source of data

It is recommended that the data being used to create type specimen Wikidata items be sourced from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF <https://www.gbif.org/>). The above discussed data model for type specimen Wikidata items has been [mapped to the Darwin Core standard](#) (<https://dwc.tdwg.org/>), the data standard used for occurrence data in GBIF. As a result, data sourced from GBIF can be easily converted into the Wikidata statements needed to enrich newly created Wikidata items for type specimens. This reduces the work required to prepare the type specimen data for upload into Wikidata. As an example see [this spreadsheet](#) based on data obtained from the GBIF New Zealand Arthropod - Symbiota dataset.

GBIF also mints a DOI for each download of data. This DOI can be used as a reference supporting the creation of the data statements enriching a newly created type specimen Wikidata item. This helps ensure the items created meet the Wikidata notability criteria as the DOI helps provide proof the type specimen has been described using serious and publicly available references.

GBIF/OpenRefine/Wikidata workflow

Downloading data from GBIF

In order to download data from GBIF you will need to set up an account linked to your email address so that GBIF has an address to send the email providing you with the link to the data you wish to download.

PUBLISHER | SINCE SEPTEMBER 27, 2012

Landcare Research

[ABOUT](#) [METRICS](#) [HOME PAGE](#)

2,632,131 OCCURRENCES
 2,580,942 HOSTED OCCURRENCES
 10 DATASETS
 1,937 CITATIONS

Wilton A (2026). Landcare Research publisher page. The blue tab can be used to access the datasets published by Landcare Research. Accessed via GBIF.org on 2026-02-25. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Once logged into GBIF, to obtain type specimen data, search GBIF to locate the appropriate dataset supplying the type specimen data. If uncertain about the name of the dataset, search for the institution that has published that dataset and from the GBIF profile for the publishing institution link through to the needed dataset.

Occurrences
GBIF API
Species
Datasets
Occurrence snapshots
Hosted portals
Trends

Get data How-to Tools Community About

REGISTERED MAY 3, 2010

Allan Herbarium (CHR)

Published by Landcare Research
Wilton A
collectors & determiners 675

ACTIVITY DOWNLOAD HOME PAGE

357,883 OCCURRENCES 1,594 CITATIONS

Specimen data from the Allan Herbarium (CHR), Landcare Research, New Zealand.

Publication date: February 16, 2026
Metadata last modified: February 15, 2026
Hosted by: Landcare Research
Licence: CC BY 4.0
How to cite: 10.15468/x5ucvh

357,883 Occurrences 99.1% With taxon match 79% With coordinates 89% With year

283,307 GEOREFERENCED RECORDS

Generated 2 days ago by OpenStreetMap contributors, © OpenMapTiles, GBIF.

Any year 1769 - 2025 EXPLORE

<https://www.gbif.org/dataset/search>

Wilton A (2026). Allan Herbarium (CHR). Landcare Research. Occurrence dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/x5ucvh> accessed via GBIF.org on 2026-02-17. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Once the relevant dataset has been located press the "Occurrences" tab on the top righthand side of the dataset.

Get data How-to Tools Community About

Occurrences

SEARCH OCCURRENCES | 357,883 RESULTS

TABLE GALLERY MAP TAXONOMY METRICS DOWNLOAD

Search all fields

Simple filters All filters

	Scientific name	Country or area	Coordinates	Event date	Occurrence status	Basis of record	Dataset
Taxon	<i>Olea fimbriata</i> Heads	New Zealand	44.5S, 170.3E	2025 Jan 20	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Verbatim taxon ID	<i>Ranunculus foliosus</i> Kirk	New Zealand	43.7S, 172.7E	2025 Jan 12	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Scientific name	<i>Araujia hortorum</i> E.Fourn.	New Zealand	43.5S, 172.6E	2025 Jan 06	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Verbatim scientific name	<i>Carex phacota</i> Spreng.	New Zealand	42.6S, 171.5E	2025 Jan 25	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
IUCN Global Red List Category	<i>Trifolium campestre</i> Schreb.	New Zealand	39.0S, 176.6E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Location	<i>Pseudognaphalium lanatum</i> (G.Forst) Sm...	New Zealand	38.9S, 176.4E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Higher geography	<i>Ranunculus flammula</i> L.	New Zealand	38.9S, 176.4E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Continent	<i>Hypericum pusillum</i> Choisy	New Zealand	38.9S, 176.4E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Water body	<i>Trifolium glomeratum</i> L.	New Zealand	39.0S, 176.6E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Island group	<i>Hypericum humifusum</i> L.	New Zealand	38.9S, 176.4E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Island	<i>Coprosma repens</i> A.Rich. × <i>Coprosma lu...</i>	New Zealand	46.6S, 168.3E	2025 Jan 27	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Country or area	<i>Carex otrubae</i> Podp.	New Zealand	40.2S, 176.7E	2025 Jan 16	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
State province							

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Then press the "All filters" tab on the top lefthand side of the occurrence data list.

The screenshot shows the GBIF Occurrences search results for the query "Highest biogeographic zone". The search returned 357,883 results. The left sidebar shows filters for "Type status" and "Identified by". The main table lists the following data:

Group	Scientific name	Country or area	Coordinates	Event date	Occurrence status	Basis of record	Dataset
Formation	<i>Olearia fimbriata</i> Heads	New Zealand	44.5S, 170.3E	2025 Jan 20	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Member	<i>Ranunculus foliosus</i> Kirk	New Zealand	43.7S, 172.7E	2025 Jan 12	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Bed	<i>Araujia hortorum</i> E.Fourn.	New Zealand	43.5S, 172.6E	2025 Jan 06	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Identification	<i>Carex phacota</i> Spreng.	New Zealand	42.6S, 171.5E	2025 Jan 25	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Type status	<i>Trifolium campestre</i> Schreb.	New Zealand	39.0S, 176.6E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Search	<i>Pseudognaphalium lanatum</i> (G.Forst) Sm...	New Zealand	38.9S, 176.4E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Ranunculus flammula</i> L.	New Zealand	38.9S, 176.4E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Hypericum pusillum</i> Choisy	New Zealand	38.9S, 176.4E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Trifolium glomeratum</i> L.	New Zealand	39.0S, 176.6E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Hypericum humifusum</i> L.	New Zealand	38.9S, 176.4E	2025 Jan 08	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Coprosma repens</i> A.Rich. = <i>Coprosma</i> L.	New Zealand	46.6S, 168.3E	2025 Jan 27	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Carex otrubae</i> Podp.	New Zealand	40.2S, 176.7E	2025 Jan 16	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Craspedia</i> G.Forst.	New Zealand	42.1S, 172.9E	2025 Jan 06	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Pinus uncinata</i> Ramond ex DC.	New Zealand	45.6S, 167.8E	2025 Jan 09	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Lonicera periclymenum</i> L.	New Zealand	45.6S, 169.0E	2025 Jan 24	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Lonicera fragrantissima</i> Lindl. & Paxton	New Zealand	41.0S, 175.6E	2025 Jan 10	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Carex divisa</i> Huds.	New Zealand	40.1S, 175.4E	2025 Jan 29	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)

Wilton A (2026). Allan Herbarium (CHR). Landcare Research. Occurrence dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/x5ucvh> accessed via GBIF.org on 2026-02-17. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Scroll down to the “Identification” filter and click the dropdown menu for “Type status”.

The screenshot shows the GBIF Occurrences search results for the query "Lowest biogeographic zone". The search returned 854 results. The left sidebar shows filters for "Type status" and "Identified by". The "Type status" filter is set to "holotype". The main table lists the following data:

Group	Scientific name	Country or area	Coordinates	Event date	Occurrence status	Basis of record	Dataset
Formation	<i>Cephalozia remotifolia</i> Glenn	New Zealand	40.9S, 172.6E	2025 Feb 14	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Member	<i>Bazzania avitata</i> Glenn	New Zealand	40.9S, 172.2E	2025 May 05	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Bed	<i>Porella atroviridis</i> Glenn & M.A.M.Renner	New Zealand	43.6S, 172.6E	2025 Jun 01	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Identification	<i>Riccardia sphagnicola</i> Glenn	New Zealand	42.9S, 171.2E	2024 Jan 10	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Type status	<i>Myosotis goyenii</i> subsp. <i>infima</i> Meudt & He...	New Zealand	43.1S, 172.6E	2019 Dec 10	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
Search	<i>Stolonivector echioides</i> Frogley & Glenn	New Zealand	43.6S, 169.9E	2018 Nov 25	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Cololejeunea velutina</i> Glenn & M.A.M.Renner	New Zealand		2018 Nov 12	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Cardamine magnifica</i> Heenan	New Zealand	43.2S, 171.7E	2017 Nov 16	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
	<i>Cardamine panatohea</i> Heenan & de Lange	New Zealand		2015 Mar 12	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)

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Select the type of type specimen required. In the above example “holotype” has been selected.

SEARCH OCCURRENCES | 854 RESULTS

TABLE GALLERY MAP TAXONOMY METRICS **DOWNLOAD**

Scientific name	Country or area	Coordinates	Event date	Occurrence status	Basis of record	Dataset
<i>Cephalozia remottifolia</i> Glenny	New Zealand	40.9S, 172.6E	2025 Feb 14	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
<i>Bazzania avittata</i> Glenny	New Zealand	40.9S, 172.2E	2025 May 05	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
<i>Porella atroviridis</i> Glenny & M.A.M.Renner	New Zealand	43.6S, 172.6E	2025 Jun 01	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
<i>Riccardia sphagnicola</i> Glenny	New Zealand	42.9S, 171.2E	2024 Jan 10	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
<i>Myosotis goyenii</i> subsp. <i>infirma</i> Meudt & He...	New Zealand	43.1S, 172.6E	2019 Dec 10	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)
<i>Stolonvector echioides</i> Frogley & Glenny	New Zealand	43.6S, 169.9E	2018 Nov 25	Present	Preserved specimen	Allan Herbarium (CHR)

Wilton A (2026). Allan Herbarium (CHR). Landcare Research. Occurrence dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/x5ucv> accessed via GBIF.org on 2026-02-17. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Press the download tab for the selected data. The data downloaded will give all those GBIF occurrences listed by the institution in that dataset as a holotype.

DOWNLOAD OPTIONS

	Raw data	Interpreted data	Multimedia	Coordinates	Format	Estimated data size
↓ SIMPLE	✗	✓	✗	✓ (if available)	Tab-delimited CSV (for use in Excel, etc.) ⓘ	460 KB (102 KB zipped for download)
↓ DARWIN CORE ARCHIVE	✓	✓	✓ (links)	✓ (if available)	Tab-delimited CSV (for use in Excel, etc.) ⓘ	1 MB (311 KB zipped for download)
↓ SPECIES LIST	✗	✓	✗	✗	Tab-delimited CSV (for use in Excel, etc.) ⓘ	
↓ CUBE	✗	✓	✗	✓ (if selected)	Tab-delimited CSV (for use in Excel, etc.) ⓘ	

DOWNLOAD REPORT

Total: 854
Licence: CC BY 4.0
Year range: 1869–2025
With year: 85 %
With coordinates: 82 %
With taxon match: 99.9 %

Known issues
A part of the GBIF processing is to flag occurrences that have suspicious fields

701 Continent derived from coordinates 103 Continent derived from country 57 Taxon match higherrank 15 Taxon match fuzzy
1 Presumed negated longitude 1 Taxon match none

https://doi.org/10.15468/x5ucv?occurrence_status=Holotype&advanced=1

Wilton A (2026). Allan Herbarium (CHR). Landcare Research. Occurrence dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/x5ucv> accessed via GBIF.org on 2026-02-17. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Select the Darwin Core Archive download as this should provide all the necessary data to create the type specimen Wikidata items. Read and agree to the notification of responsibilities regarding the downloaded data.

Hello siobhanleachman,

Your download is available at the following address:

<https://api.gbif.org/v1/occurrence/download/request/0026029-260208012135463.zip>

Citation

When using this dataset please use the following citation:

GBIF.org (18 February 2026) GBIF Occurrence Download <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.mya6xs>

Download Information

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.mya6xs> (may take some hours before being active)

Creation Date: 00:58:44 18 February 2026

Records included: 854 records from 1 published datasets

Compressed data size: 421.6 kB

Download format: DWCA

Filter used:

```
{
  "and" : [
    "DatasetKey is Allan Herbarium (CHR)",
    "TypeStatus is Holotype"
  ]
}
```

Portion of email from GBIF giving the link to the downloadable dataset zipfile and the DOI for the Occurrence dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/x5ucvh> accessed via GBIF.org on 2026-02-17. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Wait to be notified in your email with the download link. Click on the link provided in that email and download the accompanying zip file.

Uploading data into OpenRefine

Screenshot of Finder Application on Mac. Siobhan Leachman. [CCO](#)

Unzip the file to obtain the needed file. Open the OpenRefine application on the computer. See these instructions <https://openrefine.org/docs/manual/installing> if you do not have OpenRefine installed.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CCO](#)

Once you have unzipped the file and opened OpenRefine, upload the occurrence.text file into OpenRefine by pressing “Create project” and selecting that file from the finder application on your computer. At this stage you may wish to name the project with a name that includes the GBIF generated DOI.

Then press “Create project”.

OpenRefine Allan Herbarium holot

The screenshot shows the OpenRefine interface for a project named 'Allan Herbarium holot'. At the top, there is a 'Facet / Filter' section with 'Undo / Redo 4 / 4' and a back arrow. Below this are three buttons: 'Refresh', 'Reset all', and 'Remove all'. The main facet is titled 'taxonRank' and has a 'change' link. It shows '5 choices' sorted by 'name count'. The choices are: 'f.' (13), 'genus' (4), 'species' (607), 'subsp.' (84), 'var.' (140), and '(blank)' (6). There is a 'Cluster' button and a link 'Facet by choice counts' at the bottom of the facet panel.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

By selecting and including only the “species” result the facet is being used to empower the uploader to work only those occurrences that relate to holotype specimens with the taxon rank of species.

Once the editor has selected the appropriate data they wish to work on, they can then format the data to follow the data model for Wikidata items for type specimens. Again this data model can be found via the [Wikidata WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model](#). When preparing the data the editor should also ensure that any structured data statements added to Wikidata items are appropriately referenced.

Wikidata item label

Each Wikidata is required to have a label. The data model recommends that the label be “holotype of xxx” where xxx is the species name of the holotype specimen. A column in the OpenRefine project should be created for the Wikidata item label.

To create the Wikidata label column in OpenRefine the uploader will first need the name of the species to which the holotypes relate. The GBIF download normally separates the genera and the species epithet into two separate columns. By joining these it is possible to obtain the species name which can then be used when creating the Wikidata item label.

Join columns

Select and order columns to join

- genus**
- specificEpithet
- gbifID
- gbifID url
- accessRights
- bibliographicCitation
- language
- license
- modified

Select options

Separator between the content of each column
 Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to join the columns without separator.

Replace nulls with
 Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to replace nulls with blank strings.

Skip nulls.

In separator and nulls substitutes, use \n for new lines, \t for tabulation, \\n for \n, \\t for \t.

Write result in selected column.

Write result in new column named

Delete joined columns.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

In the above image the genus and specificEpithet columns are being joined with a space being the separator between the two. The two will be merged into a new column named “Wikidata item label”

<input type="button" value="▼"/> holotype of	<input type="button" value="▼"/> Wikidata item label	<input type="button" value="▼"/>
holotype of	Bazzania avittata	
holotype of	Cephaloziella remotifolia	
holotype of	Riccardia sphagnicola	
holotype of	Wettsteinia schusteriana	
holotype of	Plagiochila simpsonii	
holotype of	Allisoniella obcordata	

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

One method that can be used to create the full appropriate Wikidata item label is to also create a further column populated by the text “holotype of” and again join this column with the Wikidata item label ensuring that a space is the separator between the columns.

Join columns

Select and order columns to join

- holotype of
- Wikidata item label
- gbifID
- gbifID url
- accessRights
- bibliographicCitation
- language
- license
- modified

Select options

Separator between the content of each column

Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to join the columns without separator.

Replace nulls with

Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to replace nulls with blank strings.

Skip nulls.

In separator and nulls substitutes, use \n for new lines, \t for tabulation, \\n for \n, \\t for \t.

Write result in selected column.

Write result in new column named

Delete joined columns.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Select the two columns to be joined with the top column being the first portion of the joined column and the column underneath it being the second portion of the joined column. Highlight the column into which the joined two columns should be displayed. Then press “OK” and the two columns will be joined.

<input type="checkbox"/> Wikidata label item	<input type="checkbox"/> species name	<input type="checkbox"/> ge
holotype of <i>Bazzania avittata</i>	<i>Bazzania avittata</i>	
holotype of <i>Cephaloziella remotifolia</i>	<i>Cephaloziella remotifolia</i>	
holotype of <i>Riccardia sphagnicola</i>	<i>Riccardia sphagnicola</i>	
holotype of <i>Wettsteinia schusteriana</i>	<i>Wettsteinia schusteriana</i>	
holotype of <i>Plagiochila simpsonii</i>	<i>Plagiochila simpsonii</i>	
holotype of <i>Allisoniella obcordata</i>	<i>Allisoniella obcordata</i>	
holotype of <i>Schistochila lehmanniana</i>	<i>Schistochila lehmanniana</i>	
holotype of <i>Pterocladiastrum robustum</i>	<i>Pterocladiastrum robustum</i>	
holotype of <i>Monostroma latissimum</i>	<i>Monostroma latissimum</i>	
holotype of <i>Bryopsis moorei</i>	<i>Bryopsis moorei</i>	

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Wikidata item description

The data model recommends that the description for type specimen Wikidata items be “holotype specimen of xxx (where xxx is the full scientific name) held at xxx (where xxx is the holding institution or collection) (institution inventory number).

Again using the above methods a column can be created in the OpenRefine project that creates this description for each type specimen item.

Add column based on column catalogNumber

New column name

On error set to blank store error copy value from original column

Expression Language v

Expression No syntax error.

Preview History Starred Help

row	value	\" + value + \""
2.	CHR 700570	(CHR 700570)
3.	CHR 698205	(CHR 698205)
4.	CHR 691238	(CHR 691238)
5.	CHR 135094	(CHR 135094)
6.	CHR 685722	(CHR 685722)
7.	CHR 685654	(CHR 685654)

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This includes creating a new item with the catalogue number in brackets. The above image shows the GREL expression needed to create brackets around text in a column.

▼ Wikidata label item	▼ description
holotype of <i>Bazzania avittata</i>	holotype specimen of <i>Bazzania avittata</i> (CHR 700570)
holotype of <i>Cephaloziella remotifolia</i>	holotype specimen of <i>Cephaloziella remotifolia</i> (CHR 698205)
holotype of <i>Riccardia sphagnicola</i>	holotype specimen of <i>Riccardia sphagnicola</i> (CHR 691238)
holotype of <i>Wettsteinia schusteriana</i>	holotype specimen of <i>Wettsteinia schusteriana</i> (CHR 135094)
holotype of <i>Plagiochila simpsonii</i>	holotype specimen of <i>Plagiochila simpsonii</i> (CHR 685722)
holotype of <i>Allisoniella obcordata</i>	holotype specimen of <i>Allisoniella obcordata</i> (CHR 685654)

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

By joining this column to the Wikidata label item the editor is able to create a new column for the item description.

Instance of

A column should be created to ensure an “instance of” statement can be added to the Wikidata. For the example used in this documentation the “instance of” statement for all the items will be “holotype”. However this may differ where the OpenRefine project has different kinds of type specimens that are having Wikidata items created for them.

	instance of
09	holotype Choose new match
32	holotype Choose new match
79	holotype Choose new match

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The “instance of” column should then be reconciled against Wikidata by selecting the drop down menu, choosing “Reconcile” then selecting “Start reconciling ...”. Select the type of Wikidata entity to be reconciled against - in this case “type specimen” - and then start the reconciliation.

Collection

Where the collection that holds the specimens and the institution that is responsible for that collection differ (for example Allan Herbarium and Manaak Whenau - Landcare Research), then a column should be created for each in OpenRefine.

▼ Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research	▼ type	▼ institutionID	▼ collectionID	▼ datasetID	▼ Allan Herbarium
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match					Allan Herbarium Choose new match
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match					Allan Herbarium Choose new match
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match					Allan Herbarium Choose new match
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match					Allan Herbarium Choose new match
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match					Allan Herbarium Choose new match
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match					Allan Herbarium Choose new match
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match					Allan Herbarium Choose new match
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match					Allan Herbarium Choose new match
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match					Allan Herbarium Choose new match

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

In the above example, columns for both the Allan Herbarium, the collection where the holotypes are held, as well as Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research, the holding institution as given in GBIF, have been created.

Inventory number

▼ catalogNumber
CHR 700570
CHR 698205
CHR 691238

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

A column giving the institution inventory numbers for each of the specimens should already exist in the OpenRefine project as the GBIF download lists this inventory number in a column titled “catalogNumber”.

Collection data

eventDate

1961-11-29

1945-12

1945-04-02

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

A column providing the collection date of the species should already exist in OpenRefine as the GBI download provides this data in a column titled “eventDate”.

Location collected

Add column based on column verbatimLocality

New column name

On error set to blank store error copy value from original column

Expression Language No syntax error.

Preview History Starred Help

row	value	value
2.	Western Nelson, Heaphy River	Western Nelson, Heaphy River
3.	South Island, Western Nelson, slopes between Lake Clara and Boulder Lake	South Island, Western Nelson, slopes between Lake Clara and Boulder Lake
4.	Newton Range, Mt Brown	Newton Range, Mt Brown
5.	South Is. Fiordland, Cascade Creek	South Is. Fiordland, Cascade Creek
6.	Head of Lake Manapouri to Willmott Pass	Head of Lake Manapouri to Willmott Pass
7.	Waipoua River, North Auckland (Waipoua Forest)	Waipoua River, North Auckland (Waipoua Forest)

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The data giving the location the specimen was collected is provided by the GBIF download in a column titled “verbatimLocality”. It is recommended that this column be replicated by selecting the dropdown menu at the top of that column, selecting “Edit column” then “Add column based on this column” and providing the generated column with a new title such as “location collected” or “site_location_locality”.

The “verbatimLocality” column should be kept unreconciled to ensure that any locality statements made on Wikidata items can be qualified with a statement giving the name string for the locality as given on the specimen label.

verbatimLocality	location collected
Western Nelson, Heaphy River	Heaphy River Choose new match
South Island, Western Nelson, slopes between Lake Clara and Boulder Lake	Tasman District Choose new match
Newton Range, Mt Brown	Newton Range Choose new match
South Is. Fiordland, Cascade Creek	Fiordland Choose new match
Head of Lake Manapouri to Willmott Pass	Lake Manapouri Choose new match
Waipoua River, North Auckland (Waipoua Forest)	Waipoua River Choose new match
Stewart Island, Ulva Island	Ulva Island Choose new match
Hokianga, west coast Northland	Hokianga, west coast Northland <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match
Back water, Waikanae Estuary	Back water, Waikanae Estuary <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match
Ocean Beach, Cape Kidnappers, Hawkes Bay, east coast North Island	Ocean Beach, Cape Kidnappers, Hawkes Bay, east coast North Island <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

After the “location collected” or “site_location_locality” column has been created, it should be reconciled against Wikidata. It may be that only a small proportion of verbatim locations can be reconciled against Wikidata. Where the specific locality does not have a Wikidata item to reconcile to, it is recommended that the uploader reconcile the locality data against appropriate Wikidata items relating to a more general geographical area. For example in the above figure the verbatim “South Island, Western Nelson, slopes between Lake Clara and Boulder Lake” has been reconciled against the Wikidata item for the Tasman District which, although a more general location, encompasses the location described.

Coordinate location

Join columns

Select and order columns to join

- decimalLatitude
- decimalLongitude
- gbifID
- instance of
- gbifID url
- accessRights
- bibliographicCitation
- language
- license

Select options

Separator between the content of each column
 Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to join the columns without separator.

Replace nulls with
 Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to replace nulls with blank strings.

Skip nulls.

In separator and nulls substitutes, use \n for new lines, \t for tabulation, \\n for \n, \\t for \t.

Write result in selected column.

Write result in new column named

Delete joined columns.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The GBIF dataset will provide columns for both the longitude and latitude coordinates. To obtain an appropriate coordinate location column in the OpenRefine project, join these columns together with a comma being the separator between each column. This new column will provide the appropriate coordinate location value for the equivalent statement in Wikidata.

<input type="checkbox"/> decimalLatitude	<input type="checkbox"/> coordinate location	<input type="checkbox"/> decimalLongitude
-40.920000	-40.920000,172.150000	172.150000
-40.894945	-40.894945,172.562818	172.562818
-42.869608	-42.869608,171.201487	171.201487
-44.905102	-44.905102,168.095615	168.095615
-45.438900	-45.438900,167.373000	167.373000
-35.651202	-35.651202,173.555713	173.555713
-46.933087	-46.933087,168.136263	168.136263
-35.529366	-35.529366,173.360246	173.360246

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Nomenclatural type of

To make a “Nomenclatural type of” statement on a type specimen Wikidata item, the OpenRefine project will need a column for the species names to which the holotype specimens relate.

Join columns

Select and order columns to join

- genus**
- specificEpithet
- gbifID
- gbifID url
- accessRights
- bibliographicCitation
- language
- license
- modified

Select options

Separator between the content of each column

Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to join the columns without separator.

Replace nulls with

Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to replace nulls with blank strings.

Skip nulls.

In separator and nulls substitutes, use \n for new lines, \t for tabulation, \\n for \n, \\t for \t.

Write result in selected column.

Write result in new column named

Delete joined columns.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

If a species name column does not already exist, it can again be created by joining the genus column and the specificEpithet column with a space separator between the two.

species name

Bazzania avittata
Choose new match

Cephaloziella remotifolia
 Create new item
Search for match

Riccardia sphagnicola
 Create new item
Search for match

Wettsteinia schusteriana
Choose new match

Blaschkeia simpsonii

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Once created, the column should then be reconciled against Wikidata. It may be that some species names do not yet have a Wikidata item. It is recommended that a new Wikidata item be created for any missing taxon. For guidance on manually creating a new Wikidata item for a species see [Creating a new Wikidata taxon item](#). Information on the process of creating species Wikidata items in bulk can be found in this document [Biota of New Zealand IDs to Wikidata Workflow](#).

Collector

recordedBy
David Glenny
J Burrell George Anderson Macdonald Scott Jane Taylor
George Simpson
Kenneth W. Allison

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The collector data is provided via the “recordedBy” column from the GBIF download. This column may contain multiple collector name strings separated by a pipe “|”. In order to make a collector statement on the type specimen Wikidata item the multiple collector name strings will have to be separated out into different columns. The name strings in the cells in each of these columns should then be reconciled against Wikidata.

recordedBy	recordedByID
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facet ▶ Text filter Edit cells ▶ Edit column ▶ Transpose ▶ Sort... View ▶ Reconcile ▶ 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Split into several columns... Join columns... Add column based on this column... Add column by fetching URLs... Add columns from reconciled values... 	

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

To separate the multiple name strings into separate columns, click the dropdown menu for the recordedBy column, choose “Edit column” and select “Split into several columns ...”.

Split column "recordedBy" into several columns

How to split column

by separator

Separator regular expression

Split into columns at most (leave blank for no limit)

by field lengths

List of integers separated by commas, e.g. 5, 7, 15

After splitting

Guess cell type

Remove this column

OK

Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

To separate the columns, select the dropdown menu at the top of the "recordedBy" column, select "Edit column" and then "Split into several columns ...". Separate based on the pipe "|" and then press ok.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This will generate multiple "recordedBy" columns that should then be reconciled against Wikidata. Care should be taken to ensure each collector is appropriately disambiguated and matched to the correct Wikidata item. If needed, the editor can create a new Wikidata item for any collector that does not have a Wikidata item.

For further guidance on creating Wikidata items for collectors of specimens see this teaching resource [Integrating Wikidata with Data Sleuthing Techniques For Enhanced Knowledge Discovery of Hidden Figures.](#)

Specimen classifier

A screenshot of the 'identifiedBy' column dropdown menu in OpenRefine. The menu is open, showing a list of specimen determiner name strings. The strings are: 'Phil M. Novis', 'Phil M. Novis | J. Braidwood | C. Kilroy', 'Phil M. Novis | J. Braidwood | C. Kilroy', 'Phil M. Novis', 'Phil M. Novis', 'Phil M. Novis | J. Braidwood | C. Kilroy', 'Una V. Cassie Cooper | G.P. Dempsey', and 'Peter R. Heenan'.

identifiedBy
Phil M. Novis
Phil M. Novis J. Braidwood C. Kilroy
Phil M. Novis J. Braidwood C. Kilroy
Phil M. Novis
Phil M. Novis
Phil M. Novis J. Braidwood C. Kilroy
Una V. Cassie Cooper G.P. Dempsey
Peter R. Heenan

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The specimen determiner data is provided via the “identifiedBy” column from the GBIF download. This column may again contain multiple specimen determiner name strings separated by pipe “|”. Similar to the collector columns, in order to make a determiner statement on the type specimen Wikidata item the multiple determiner name strings will have to be separated out into different columns and reconciled against Wikidata.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Again, click the dropdown menu for the “identifiedBy” column, choose “Edit column” and select “Split into several columns ...”.

Split column "identifiedBy" into several columns

<p>How to split column</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> by separator</p> <p>Separator <input type="text" value=" "/> <input type="checkbox"/> regular expression</p> <p>Split into <input type="text" value=""/> columns at most (leave blank for no limit)</p> <p><input type="radio"/> by field lengths</p> <p><input type="text" value=""/></p> <p>List of integers separated by commas, e.g. 5, 7, 15</p>	<p>After splitting</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Guess cell type</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Remove this column</p>
---	--

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Separate the columns based on the pipe “|” and then press ok.

Described by source

It is possible to add a statement linking the type specimen Wikidata items to a published source. The published source should have its own item in Wikidata. If this statement is able to be applied to all the type specimen Wikidata items the editor can add a column to OpenRefine for the source. Once reconciled against Wikidata the data in that column can be used to create a statement ensuring the new type specimen Wikidata items links to the Wikidata item for that source.

Described at URL

It is highly recommended that a statement be added to the type specimen Wikidata item linking to the GBIF occurrence URL.

All	gbifID	gbif occurrence id url
☆	1. 5294384605	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294384605
☆	2. 5294384034	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294384034
☆	3. 5294383629	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294383629
☆	4. 5294383437	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294383437
☆	5. 5294382737	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294382737
☆	6. 5294382688	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294382688
☆	7. 5294382679	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294382679

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

A column giving this URL can be formed by creating a column with “<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/>” as a text string in all the cells of that column and then joining that column with the gbifID column with no separator. This will create cells with the appropriate URL for each GBIF occurrence record. For further information see the section on gbifID column in the below References section.

references
https://scd.landcareresearch.co.nz/Specimen/CHR_700570
https://scd.landcareresearch.co.nz/Specimen/CHR_698205
https://scd.landcareresearch.co.nz/Specimen/CHR_691238

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

It is also recommended that, where possible, a statement be added to the type specimen Wikidata item linking to the institution's collection record URL. A column giving that collection record URL may already exist in the GBIF download in a “references” column.

Significant event

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Where the type specimen is connected to a significant event, for example if it was collected during a research expedition, editors are encouraged to add this data to the type specimen Wikidata item via the “[significant event](#)” (P793) property.

This data is unlikely to be contained in the GBIF download unless the institution has linked the type specimen to the Wikidata item QID for the research expedition via the Darwin Core term “parentEventID”. If the institution has this data in GBIF, the editor can reconcile that column against Wikidata and then add a “significant event” statement to the type specimen Wikidata item.

Sex or gender

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

A column should already exist in the OpenRefine project as a result of GBIF download containing a column titled “sex”. If the GBIF download contains data on the sex of the organism, this column can be reconciled against Wikidata to prepare for a “sex or gender” statement being added to the type specimen Wikidata item.

Biological phase

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This column should already exist in the OpenRefine project as a result of the GBIF download containing a “lifeStage” column. If the GBIF download contains data on the life stage of the specimen organism, this column can be reconciled against Wikidata to prepare for a “biological phase” statement being added to the type specimen Wikidata items.

References

It is important to ensure that any statement made in a Wikidata item is appropriately referenced. It is therefore recommended that before the upload of the prepared data to Wikidata is completed references be prepared in OpenRefine to support any statements made in the newly created holotype specimen Wikidata items. These references can then be added when creating the OpenRefine schema to assist with the upload of data to Wikidata.

	publisher	references	rightsHolder
		https://scd.landcareresearch.co.nz/Specimen/CHR_700599	Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research NZ Ltd.
00		https://scd.landcareresearch.co.nz/Specimen/CHR_700570	Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research NZ Ltd.
		https://scd.landcareresearch.co.nz/Specimen/CHR_698205	Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research NZ Ltd.
00		https://scd.landcareresearch.co.nz/Specimen/CHR_691238	Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research NZ Ltd.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The dataset downloaded from GBIF and used to create an OpenRefine project may contain a reference column providing a URL link to specimen as provided by the institution's database. It is also recommended that the GBIF occurrence URL be cited to support the validity of statements made in the type specimen Wikidata items. Finally the downloaded GBIF dataset will also have a Digital Object Identifier or DOI associated with it. Editors are encouraged to use this DOI as a reference to support the statements made in Wikidata.

gbifID column

This column provides the GBIF occurrence id for each of the holotype specimens. This column can be used to help create a new column giving the GBIF occurrence URL for each specimen.

	gbifID	datasetKey	occurrenceID
1.		3b58-11dc-8c19-b8a03c50a862	BE4342F1-BB2F-472
2.		3b58-11dc-8c19-b8a03c50a862	8D472702-1371-44A
3.			0A
4.			49
5.			3A
6.	4429298348	df582950	49F
7.	4429298336	df582950	4B
8.	4429297476	df582950	438
9.	4429295308	df582950	46
10.	4173259651	df582950	4A

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Generate a new column by pressing the dropdown menu for the column, selecting “Edit column” and then “Adding column based on this column...”.

Add column based on column gbifID

New column name

On error set to blank store error copy value from original column

Expression Language ▾

No syntax error.

Preview History Starred Help

row	value	blank
1.	5213566421	null
2.	5213551409	null
3.	5083396332	null
4.	4903556079	null
5.	4435328309	null
6.	4429298348	null

OK

Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Name the new column gbif occurrence id url and replace the word “value” in the GREL box with the word “blank”. Then press ok.

gbif occurrence id url	datasetKey	occurrenceID
	df582950-3b58-11dc-8c19-b8a03c50a862	5930D7DD-EA49-4975-92B8-BBF02FA
	df582950-3b58-11dc-8c19-b8a03c50a862	16669431-E82E-43AB-BA62-16A82DB
	df582950-3b58-11dc-8c19-b8a03c50a862	2546CD46-4F5B-49F3-95F8-C76E23C

Data type: ▾

Enter Ctrl-Enter Esc

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Edit the first cell in the new column by adding “<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/>” and then press “Apply to all identical cells”. This will add this portion of the URL to all the cells in this column.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Then select the dropdown menu for the GBIF occurrence id column and then select “Edit column”, “Join columns ...”.

Join columns

Select and order columns to join

- gbif occurrence id url
- gbifID
- datasetKey
- occurrenceID
- kingdom
- phylum
- class
- order
- family

Select all Deselect all

Select options

Separator between the content of each column

Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to join the columns without separator.

Replace nulls with

Enter one or more characters, or keep blank to replace nulls with blank strings.

Skip nulls.

In separator and nulls substitutes, use \n for new lines, \t for tabulation, \\n for \n, \\t for \t.

Write result in selected column.

Write result in new column named

Delete joined columns.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

In the popup box select the GBIF occurrence id url column. Also select the gbifID column. Ensure the GBIF occurrence id url column is highlighted so the result of the joining will be written in that column. There should be no separator between the two columns; none is needed to generate the full url.

gbifID	gbif occurrence id url
5213566421	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5213566421
5213551409	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5213551409
5083396332	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5083396332
4903556079	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4903556079
4435328309	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4435328309
4429298348	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4429298348
4429298336	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4429298336
4429297476	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4429297476
4429295308	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4429295308
4173259651	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4173259651

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The result will be a column populated with the full url for each GBIF occurrence in the downloaded dataset.

Uploading data to Wikidata

Creating a schema

Once the needed data in the OpenRefine project is prepared and appropriately reconciled against Wikidata it is now time to create the Schema for the data upload.

The first step is to inform OpenRefine that new Wikidata items are to be created for the type specimens in the project.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Do this by attempting to reconcile the Wikidata label item column against Wikidata.

Reconcile column Wikidata label item

Select a service to reconcile against:

<input type="radio"/>	Wikimedia Commons (en) https://commonsreconcile.toolforge.org/en/api	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Wikidata reconcil.link (en) https://wikidata.reconcil.link/en/api	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
<input type="radio"/>	ORCID https://refine.codefork.com/reconcile/orcid	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
<input type="radio"/>	Bionomia https://api.bionomia.net/reconcile	<input type="button" value="✕"/>

Add standard service...

Discover services...

Next »

Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Choose Wikidata as the reconciliation service.

Reconcile column Wikidata label item

Reconcile each cell to an entity of one of these types:

<input checked="" type="radio"/>	entity Q35120
----------------------------------	------------------

Also use relevant details from other columns:

Column	As property
gbifID	<input type="text"/>
instance of	<input type="text"/>
gbifID url	<input type="text"/>
accessRights	<input type="text"/>
bibliographicCitation	<input type="text"/>
language	<input type="text"/>
license	<input type="text"/>
modified	<input type="text"/>
publisher	<input type="text"/>
references	<input type="text"/>
Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research	<input type="text"/>
type	<input type="text"/>

Reconcile against type:

Reconcile against no particular type

Auto-match candidates with high confidence

Maximum number of candidates to return

Back

Start reconciling...

Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Reconcile against the “entity” type.

Wikidata label item	description	species name
tata	holotype specimen of Bazzania avittata (CHR 700570)	Bazzania avittata Choose new match
remotifolia	holotype specimen of Cephaloziella remotifolia (CHR 698205)	Cephaloziella remotifolia Choose new match
sphagnicola	holotype specimen of Riccardia sphagnicola (CHR 691238)	Riccardia sphagnicola Choose new match

holotype of Wettsteinia s...
[Create new item](#)
[Search for match](#)

holotype of Plagiochila s...
[Create new item](#)
[Search for match](#)

holotype of Allisoniella o...
[Create new item](#)
[Search for match](#)

holotype of Schistochila l...
[Create new item](#)
[Search for match](#)

4920) [Choose new match](#)

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Of course because these type specimens do not yet have a Wikidata item to reconcile against, OpenRefine will fail to reconcile the cells in this column. Instead OpenRefine provides the option of creating a new item for each of the type specimens. To undertake this for all the cells in the column, select the dropdown menu at the top of the column, go to “Reconcile” then “Actions” and then select “Create a new item for each cell ...”

Wikidata label item
holotype of Bazzania avittata new Choose new match
holotype of Cephaloziella remotifolia new Choose new match
holotype of Riccardia sphagnicola new Choose new match

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This will instruct OpenRefine to create a new item that follows the schema about to be created.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Then go to the top righthand side of the OpenRefine project and select the dropdown menu of the extensions Wikibase. Select “Edit Wikibase schema”.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Then select the “Schema” tab at the top of the page, select Wikidata as the Target Wikibase instance and then press the “Add item” button at the bottom lefthand side. Select “Label” from the dropdown menu.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Add the reconciled “Wikidata label item” column to the “type item or drag reconciled item” box, as the column has been reconciled and OpenRefine has been instructed to create new items with this column. Press “+ add term” and select “Label” from the dropdown menu. Use the same reconciled “Wikidata label item” column for the label, ensuring that the appropriate language for that label is also chosen.

Click “+ add term” then click the Terms dropdown menu again and select “Description”. Again choose the appropriate language and then drag and drop the prepared “description” column into the appropriate box.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Then press “+ add statement” to continue adding statements that will make up the schema for the new type specimen Wikidata items. Follow the Natural history type specimen data model set out in [Wikidata:WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model](#) to ensure the schema is consistent with best practice recommendations. See below for images of an example schema.

Example OpenRefine schema for a type specimen Wikidata item project

Wikidata label item

 remove

Terms

Label	en	Wikidata label item remove		
Description	en	description remove		

[+ add term](#)

Statements
no statements added

[+ add statement](#)

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Statements

instance of	typeStat...	paste reference + add reference + add value
collection	Holding institut...	remove + add qualifier + add reference
	object of state holding institution	
collection	Holding collect...	remove + add qualifier + add reference + add value
	object of state holding collection	
inventory number	catalogNum...	paste reference + add reference + add value
	collection collectionCo...	

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collection date	eventDate	remove configure + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value
coordinate location	location coordina...	remove configure + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value
nomenclatural type c	species subject has rol holotype	remove configure remove + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value
collector	recordedB... recordedB...	remove configure + add qualifier paste reference + add reference remove configure + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value

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specimen classifier	identifiedB... point in time datelidentifi...	remove configure remove + add qualifier paste reference + add reference
	identifiedB... point in time datelidentifi...	remove configure remove + add qualifier paste reference + add reference
	identifiedB... point in time datelidentifi...	remove configure remove + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value
location collected	locality object named text string of lo...	remove configure remove + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value

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The above screenshots are an example of a schema for a type specimen Wikidata item OpenRefine project.

Checking before upload

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Before asking OpenRefine to create the new type specimen Wikidata items, check the “Issues” tab to ensure any issues raised that can be dealt with have been.

595 matching rows (854 total)

Schema *

Issues 595

Preview

This tab shows the first edits (out of 595) that will be made once you upload the changes to [Wikidata](#). You can u

holotype of *Bazzania avittata* (new item)

Label (do not override)	holotype of <i>Bazzania avittata</i> (English)	
Description (do not override)	holotype specimen of <i>Bazzania avittata</i> (CHR 700570) (English)	
inventory number (P217)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CHR 700570 collection (P195) Allan Herbarium (Q50807570) 	▶ 1 references
collection (P195)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research (Q1801980) object of statement has role (P3831) holding institution (Q131597993) 	▶ 1 references
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allan Herbarium (Q50807570) object of statement has role (P3831) holding collection (Q137935182) 	▶ 1 references
instance of (P31)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> holotype (Q1061403) 	▶ 2 references

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Also check the “Preview” tab to ensure the data will be uploaded as expected.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

If the uploader is confident the issues raised in the issues tab have been dealt with and the preview examples as shown in the preview tab align with the uploader's expectations, it is now time to upload the data to Wikidata and create the new type specimen Wikidata items. If the uploader is creating a large number of new Wikidata items, it is highly recommended the uploader consider creating a small batch of new items before completing the full upload.

To ask OpenRefine to create the new items go to the top righthand side of the OpenRefine project and click on the Wikibase dropdown menu. Select "Upload edits to Wikibase ...". Double check the edits are being uploaded to Wikidata.

Upload edits to Wikidata

You are about to upload 595 edits to [Wikidata](#). Please check them carefully. Large edit batches should be submitted for [bot review](#) first.

This edit batch will create new Wikidata items.
Locate rows
595

Please make sure that these items do not exist yet and are [suitable for inclusion in Wikidata](#).

You are logged in as: [Ambrosia10](#).

summary

maxlag Must be a positive integer. Leave this to the default value unless you know [how maxlag works](#).

Cancel

Upload edits

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Fill in a summary of the upload about to be undertaken and then press the "Upload edits" button on the bottom right hand side.

Allow time for the edits to take place. This can take some time for larger projects as uploads of data via OpenRefine are rate limited.

Once the upload is finished it is worth returning to the "Wikidata label item" column in the OpenRefine project and clicking on the link to the newly created Wikidata item to check whether the upload proceeded as expected.

Other related links

- [Wikidata data model for Natural History type specimens](#)
- [Crosswalk for Natural History Specimen Data Model - Wikidata](#)
- [New Zealand Arthropod Collection holotype specimen Wikidata upload](#)
- [Information on different tools for processing and importing data into Wikidata](#)